

Factors Affecting the Satisfaction of Employees Civil Service in the Health Ministry District Tolikara

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ABSTRACT

Background: Job satisfaction is very important to be considered by Tolikara District Health Office. Satisfied employees tend to perform well while disgruntled employees tend to be more often daydreaming, lack of enthusiasm in work, fatigue, boredom, unstable emotions and unrelated activities. Factors affecting the work are influenced by factors from within the self include motivation and work discipline while external factors include reward, punishment, organizational culture and leadership.

Methods: Descriptive analytic with quantitative correlative approach conducted in March 2018 with a total sample of 64 people. Data were obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression.

Result of research: There are influence of motivation ($p = 0,000$), reward ($p = 0,040$), punishment ($p = 0,000$), organizational culture ($p = 0,000$) and leadership ($p = 0,000$). While the work discipline has no significant effect on the job satisfaction of civil servants in Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,136$). Together there is the influence of motivation, work discipline, reward, punishment, organizational culture and leadership towards employee job satisfaction at Tolikara District Health Office and have contribution to job satisfaction of 89.5%. Punishment is dominant factor to job satisfaction.

Key Words: Satisfaction of job, Employee Government, Health Ministry

1. INTRODUCTION

The health service as a facility in providing health services to the community

is required to have good quality health services. The demands and needs of the community for quality health services need to be addressed by improving the quality of human resources. Therefore, human resources, especially in the health sector, play an important role as a driving source of programs in the health sector. The role of human resources also determines the health status of a country which can be seen in several health indicators (Misnaniarti, 2010; Rantetampang, 2014). This condition explains that the quality of human resources determines the quality of the process to be carried out, so as to produce good goals. This can be realized if human resources are able to work better with high job satisfaction (Djestawana, 2012).

Job satisfaction is very important to be considered by the Tolikara District Health Office. Job satisfaction can be observed directly through expressions of feelings expressed in certain statements or behaviors (Wijaya, 2012). Employees who feel satisfied working have a level of attendance and sometimes have better performance than employees who are not satisfied working (Handoko, 2010). In addition, employees who feel satisfied tend to have good performance, have a low level of absenteeism and a low desire to change jobs (Robbins, 2008). Employees who are dissatisfied with work tend to daydream more often, lack enthusiasm at work, quickly experience fatigue, get bored quickly, emotionally unstable and do activities that are not related to work

(Wibisono, 2011). In addition, the impact caused by dissatisfaction can be seen in the slow pace of employees at work, high level of absenteeism, negligence, low achievement, low product quality and employee discipline problems (David, 2011). This shows job satisfaction is an important aspect for employees and organizations, especially because it is able to create a positive state in the organizational environment.

Tolikara District Health Office has a large number of employees consisting of civil servants and contract workers in order to achieve goals effectively and powerfully to require the division of labor, delegation of authority and responsibility, unity of command, unity of direction, discipline to the details of the task each employee involved in the organization. In addition, in an organization must be responsible and collaborate well with all employees in the organization to create conducive conditions to support the process of achieving organizational goals. The initial survey was in December 2017 that the number of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office was 64 people, with an attendance rate of 80%. In general, the level of attendance seen from work attendance attendance is quite high, but the number of civil servants in the office to carry out their duties is less than 80% of the number of attendees. From the survey results, only around 40% of civil servants in the Health Office were ready to carry out their duties, while the rest were outside, not present, out for unknown purposes and various other things (Data Attendance of Tolikara District Health Office, 2017; Salmah, et, al 2014: Mallongi, et, al, 2017)

Every day, civil servants at the Tolikara District Health Office are on must attend work at 08.00 WIB, and come home at 12.00 WIB, then come back to work at 14.00 WIB until 17.00 WIB, this working hour is valid from Monday to Friday. However, the working hours that have been determined are often only a rule without being obeyed by some of the civil servants

in the Tolikara District Health Office. The Tolikara District Health Office is a government agency in the area whose task is managing the health sector in Tolikara District. Every organization always wants to have the workforce capable of increasing high productivity. Similarly, the Tolikara District Health Office, which is very responsible for all health programs carried out for the benefit of health services, must be able to reach the entire community of Tolikara Regency. However, to achieve good health services quality human resources are needed and have good work productivity to support health programs carried out by the Tolikara District Health Office.

The health service program carried out by the Tolikara District Health Service is basically to achieve the goals of the Tolikara Regency which is healthy. However, to achieve good health services quality human resources are needed and have good work productivity to support health programs carried out by the Tolikara District Health Office. The health service program carried out by the Tolikara District Health Service is basically to achieve the goals of the Tolikara Regency which is healthy. However, to achieve these objectives, the productivity of Civil Servants in the Health Office must be increased to be able to make a good contribution to the health service program in Tolikara Regency. Job satisfaction of employees at the Tolikara District Health Office is influenced by various problems or factors, both related to the employee itself and other factors, such as leadership, motivation, compensation, organizational culture, level of education, skills, discipline, attitudes and work ethics, nutrition and health, income level, social security, etc. which at the end has an impact on the job satisfaction of employees in the Tolikara District Health Office. These problems must receive good attention from the leaders in the Tolikara District Office, otherwise it will influence the performance of the employee. The problem is, it is very

important to know the Head of Service in order to be able to manage and lead employees in achieving the goal of quality health services for people who live in the work area of the Tolikara District Health Office. The purpose of this study was to determine the factors that affect the job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Quantitative descriptive with a correlative approach conducted in March 2018 with a total sample of 64 people. Data were obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression.

3. RESEARCH RESULT

Simultaneous Significance Test (Test F)

Table 1. Simultaneous Significance Test

Model Summary ^b											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
						R Change	Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	
1	.951 ^a	.905	.895		1,58320	.905	90.622	6	57	.000	2.355

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leaderships, Reward, Discipline, Motivation, Punishment, Organizational cultur
b. Dependent Variable: work satisfaction

The calculation results obtained F calculated at 90.66622 while the first freedom degree (df1) = 6 and the second degree of freedom (df2) = 57, so obtained f table = 2.24. From these results (F count = 90.622) > (2.24) so that it is located in the area of Ha acceptance, it means that there is

a significant influence together - motivation (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6) on job satisfaction (Y) in the Tolikara District Health Office.

T Test

Table 2. Partial Significance Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-17.415	2.302		-7.565	.000
	Motivasi	.340	.071	.261	4.757	.000
	Discipline_Kerja	.090	.060	.066	1.513	.136
	Reward	.121	.058	.088	2.099	.040
	Punishment	.646	.139	.467	4.658	.000
	Budaya_Organisasi	.645	.160	.437	4.037	.000
	Kepemimpinan	-.213	.067	-.204	-3.174	.002

Based on table 2 shows that the constant value is -17.415 if there is no motivation (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6), then the amount of job satisfaction (Y) amounting to -17.415.

The regression coefficient value for the motivation variable is 0.340. This shows a positive direction between motivation variables (X1) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the motivation variable (X1) changes 1% while the work discipline variable (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5)) and leadership (X6) remain, then the value of

job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.340 (34%) and the results of p-value = 0.000, which means that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees in the Tolikara District Health Office.

The regression coefficient value for the working discipline variable is 0.090. This shows a positive direction between the variables of work discipline (X2) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning if the variable work discipline (X2) changes 1% while the motivation variable (X1), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6) remain, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.090 (9%) and the results of p-value =

0.0136, which means that work discipline has no significant effect on employee job satisfaction in the District Health Office Tolikara.

The regression coefficient value for the reward variable is 0.121. This shows a positive direction between reward variables (X3) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning if the reward variable (X3) changes 1% while the motivation variable (X1), work discipline (X2), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5)) and leadership (X6) remain, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.121 (12%) and the results of p-value = 0.040, which means that reward has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction of employees in the Tolikara District Health Service.

The regression coefficient value for punishment variable is 0.646. This shows the positive direction between punishment (X4) variables on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that the punishment (X4) variable changes 1% while the motivation variable (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), organizational culture (X5)) and leadership (X6) remain, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.646 (64.6%) and the results of p-value = 0,000, which means that punishment has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction of employees in Tolikara District Health Office .

The regression coefficient value for the organizational culture variable is 0.645. This shows a positive direction between the variables of organizational culture (X5) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning if the organizational culture variable (X5) changes 1% while the motivation variable (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4) and leadership (X6) remain, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.645 (64.5%) and the results of p-value = 0,000, which means that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Health Service Tolikara Regency.

The regression coefficient value for the leadership variable is -0.213. This shows a positive direction between leadership variables (X6) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that the leadership variable (X6) changes 1% while the motivation variable (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4) and organizational culture (X5) remains, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by -0.213 (-21.3%) and the results of p-value = 0.002, which means that leadership has a negative and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Health Service Tolikara Regency.

Determination Coefficient

The magnitude of the determination value (R²) (see table 4.17) the calculated result is 0.905. This value shows that the six motivation variables (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6) in this study have contributed to employee job satisfaction variables (Y) amounting to 90.5% where the rest, which is 9.5% is explained by other variables outside this research.

4. DISCUSSION

The influence of motivation on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that motivation had a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office (p = 0,000). The motivation felt by employees in the work environment of the Tolikara District Health Office shows that the intrinsic motivation of employees given for job satisfaction 50% of leaders does not give praise for the results of employee work, 32.8% do not expect prizes in the form of money / goods to employees, 51.6% employees do not expect gratitude from the leadership for being able to complete a specific task. The extrinsic motivation felt by employees is that 43.8% of employees are not assigned to participate in a training

activity outside Papua and 45.3% involve or involve you in a committee in the office. But most of them answered well 51.6% of good leaders by giving motivation to be more enthusiastic in carrying out their tasks, 34.4% both assigning employees to take part in seminars in other institutions, 43.8% good that sanctions imposed on employees who violated the rules in this office is firm, 43.8% is good at assigning employees to complete a job outside the main duties, 42.2% of good leaders give rewards to employees who excel in their duties.

The average job satisfaction for motivation is felt by employees in the Tolikara District Health Office, where the coefficient test results show that the regression coefficient value for the motivation variable is 0.340. This shows a positive direction between motivation variables (X1) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that the motivation variable increases job satisfaction by 0.340 or 34% to job satisfaction.

The influence of work discipline on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that compensation had no significant effect on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.136$). Employees at the Tolikara District Health Office who have work discipline from the responses of respondents mostly say that they often come to work on time as many as 31 people (42.2%), often come home from work according to the time specified by 33 people (51.6%), rarely complete the task according to the time set as many as 18 people (28.1%), rarely carry out orders superiorly as many as 24 people (37.5%), rarely make mistakes if I fail to work as many as 12 people (18.8%), rarely use office facilities well as many as 19 people (29.7%), rarely work according to work procedures that have been set as many as 37 people (57.8%), rarely can adjust to changes in work procedures in office as many as 34 people (53.1%), rarely responsible for the work I do as many as 32 people (50%),

rarely looking for new knowledge and innovative ways to complete work as many as 43 people (67.2%).

Researcher's observation that employee work discipline does not affect employee morale, the level of compensation given, thus affecting employee job satisfaction. Employees who feel dissatisfied with the results of work with the compensation provided, so that they are not disciplined or obey the rules set. Employees who are not disciplined appear to enter not according to the time specified, as well as the time to go home. Employees with high morale tend to work better, on time and never ditch. Employees will be eager to go to work so that their work discipline is high. In addition, lack of punishment for work discipline affects employee productivity. In addition, several employees of the Tolikara District Health Office with low productivity were caused by the majority of employees living in Biak Numfor District with a distance of 2.5 hours to Tolikara Regency or to the Papua Provincial Health Office. This certainly has an impact on employee motivation related to the presence and timeliness of coming and going home at work.

Effect of reward on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that reward had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.040$). Reward felt by employees in the Tolikara District Health Office mostly states that most of them stated that leaders often give awards to employees who are disciplined to enter the office as many as 38 people (59.4%), often providing cash assistance to families of employees who died as many as 37 people (57.8%), rarely provide medical expenses for employees who experience accidents while carrying out duties as many as 29 people (45.3%), rarely provide educational assistance for employees who continue to education as many as 31 people (48.4%), rarely provide opportunities for those who

have good performance in career levelling as many as 43 people (67.1%), rarely give congratulations to employees who have good performance good as many as 29 people (45.3%) and leaders often pay attention to the results of the performance that you have achieved as many as 49 people (76.6%).

This shows that employees feel good salaries / wages. In addition, employees are also given the opportunity to continue their education as well as educational assistance and assistance for employees in home loans. This has indeed been regulated in personnel management and carried out by both leaders. However, in this case the leadership is less assertive in employees who are not disciplined; this affects the job satisfaction of employees who are disciplined and obedient in following the rules established in the Tolikara District Health Office.

This causes that reward has an effect on increasing employee job satisfaction. From the results of the regression coefficient for the compensation variable is 0.701. This shows a positive direction between reward variables (X3) on job satisfaction (Y), if the reward variable (X3) changes 1%, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.121 or 12.1%. This means that the rewards given or felt by employees increase job satisfaction for the results of work achieved, because employees feel the presence of attention from their work place in paying attention to the welfare of their employees.

Effect of punishment on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that punishment has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,000$). The response of employees to punishment in the Tolikara District Health Office was that most of the guards said that the leaders often gave reprimands to employees for 40 people arriving late (62.5%) and giving reprimands to employees who did not complete the work on time as many as 31 people (48 ,

4%). Most of the guards stated that leaders rarely monitor employees who do not work according to office procedures as many as 32 people (50%). Respondents stated that leaders often did not give reprimand to employees who had never entered the office without a clear reason stating that as many as 38 people (59.4%) and leaders rarely gave reprimand to employees who returned not according to office hours of 30 people (46.9%), respondents stated that 28 people (43.8%) often gave warnings to employees who were lazing in the office (43.8%) and the leaders often gave reprimand to employees who left office hours without reason which clearly stated that there were 38 people (59,4%), rarely does the leader give reprimand to employees not responsible for work according to their main duties and functions as many as 35 people (54.7%), leaders often give reprimand to employees who violate office rules stating good as many as 38 people (59.4 %) and the majority of respondents stated that the leadership rarely gave sanctions to 48 negligent employees (75%).

This causes punishment to affect employee job satisfaction. From the results of the regression coefficient for the compensation variable is 0.701. This shows a positive direction between punishment (X4) variables on job satisfaction (Y), if the punishment (X4) variable changes 1%, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.646 or 64.6%. This means that punishment given or felt by employees increases job satisfaction for the results of work achieved, because employees feel the attention of their work place in paying attention to the welfare of their employees.

The influence of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that organizational culture had a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.002$).

The organizational culture felt by employees in the Tolikara District Health

Office is not good that the respondents answered 46.9% that the leaders rarely accommodate the ideas of each employee, as many as 50% said employees were rarely given the opportunity to develop themselves, 54.7% of leaders often encouraged you to make a mature decision, 45.3% of leaders encourage employees to be more careful in working, 62.5% of leaders often prioritize results from the process, 59.4% of leaders often provide standards in the quality of work, 60.9% of leaders often create healthy competition in work, 59.4% of leaders often maintain the system and procedures in the work that applies, 45.3% of leaders often encourage you to always work in teams and 75% often work completed in teams.

This shows that the organizational culture in the Tolikara District Health Office leadership plays an important role in creating a harmonious culture between leaders and subordinates and fellow employees. This culture forms a harmonious work team in completing a work with systems and procedures that apply while being efficient and effective in achieving the target. The perceived organizational culture both increases employee job satisfaction. From the results the regression coefficient value for the organizational culture variable is 0.645. This shows a positive direction between the variables of organizational culture (X5) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the organizational culture variable (X5) changes 1%, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.645 or 64.5%

The influence of leadership on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that there was leadership influence on job satisfaction of civil servants at the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.002$). Leadership in the Work Environment Tolikara District Health Office mostly answered that 42.2% of leaders rarely created harmonious working conditions among employees, 42.2% of leaders rarely communicated all tasks to

employees clearly and 42.2% of leaders rarely valued every the opinions expressed by employees at each meeting, 50% of leaders rarely give the opportunity to convey feelings and complaints and 40.6% of leaders rarely have the friendly nature of carrying out their duties every day. Most of the respondents answered that 45.3% of leaders rarely explained the targets to be achieved in carrying out tasks, 51.6% of leaders rarely made decisions on a problem always based on the correct facts, 50% of the leaders often cooperated well, 51.6% of leaders often provide clear direction in completing the task well and 73.4% of the leaders often carry out daily tasks in accordance with work procedures in the office.

In decision making decisions in the Tolikara District Health Office 51.6% of leaders both in making decisions on a problem are always based on the right facts, 50% of leaders can cooperate well, 51.6% of leaders provide clear direction in completing the task properly and 73.4% of leaders are good at carrying out daily tasks in accordance with work procedures in the office. It was what happened in the Tolikara District Health Office that leadership was still not good for employees to lead the leadership in creating harmonious working conditions and lacking communication with subordinates to all tasks clearly assigned to employees. Exemplary although most respond both in achieving work targets, leadership cooperation and work direction according to procedures.

This is evidenced by the results of the correlation value of -0.213. This shows the negative direction between leadership variables (X1) on job satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the leadership variable (X6) changes 1%, then the value of job satisfaction (Y) will decrease by -0.213. This means that bad leadership that is assessed by employees has an impact on the decrease in job satisfaction of employees in the Tolikara District Health Office. This is important to note a leader to his subordinates that a leader is highly valued

by his subordinates so that his employees obey and obey the rules that have been set together. This is in line with the opinion of Wijaya (2007), that good leaders must be able to foster feelings of participation and responsibility for their work so as to increase employee morale which leads to job satisfaction.

Simultaneous influence of leadership, motivation, compensation, and organizational culture on employee job satisfaction

The results showed that the dominant factor or simultaneously between motivation (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6) had an effect on employee job satisfaction (Y). This means that if motivation (X1), work discipline (X2), reward (X3), punishment (X4), organizational culture (X5) and leadership (X6) simultaneously increase, it affects employee job satisfaction (Y), where from the results the value of determination (R²) in this study has a contribution to the variable employee job satisfaction (Y) of 90.5% where the rest of 9.5% is explained by other variables outside this study.

Job satisfaction of employees in the Tolikara District Health Office that most answered 46.9% badly with challenging work, 50% dissatisfied with the jobs you have done so far, 46.9% cleanliness and tidiness of workspace is not good, 46.9% experience stress when facing work that is difficult to solve. This shows that employees are still not well motivated especially with employment - challenging work, but employees feel dissatisfied with the results of the work achieved so far. This means that employees have the motivation to achieve good performance. In addition, most of the respondents answered that 48.4% were satisfied with their current assignment, 43.8% were satisfied when doing work alone without the help of others, 45.3% were able to coordinate well in doing assignments with friends, 46.9% career path

is clearly determined, 45.3% of the work you have achieved is in line with your expectations, 43.8% of your work space is fully available. This indicates that pegawai are satisfied with the physical condition of the workplace with adequate facilities and facilities as well as non-physical environment such as relationships with co-workers and a clear caring level for employees. This can not be separated from the influence of leadership as a leader, motivation, compensation policy and organizational culture carried out which led to leadership, motivation, compensation and organizational culture contributing to 88.6% job satisfaction while 11.4% can be influenced by such punishment and organizational commitment.

In general, each individual or employee in the work environment of the Tolikara District Health Office has a different educational background that influences their behavior. Applied leadership and motivation and compensation and organizational culture that lead individuals to behave and give guidance to them to handle whatever must be followed and learned. This condition also applies in an organization, namely how employees in the work environment of the Tolikara District Health Office behave and what they are supposed to do is much influenced by the culture adopted by the organization, so that partially and simultaneously influences job satisfaction.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been presented, the following conclusions are drawn:

- There is a significant influence of motivation on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,000$).
- There was no significant influence on work discipline on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.136$).
- There is a significant effect of reward on job satisfaction of civil servants in the

Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0.040$).

- There is a significant effect of punishment on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,000$).
- There is a significant influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction of civil servants in the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,000$).
- There was a significant leadership influence on the job satisfaction of civil servants at the Tolikara District Health Office ($p = 0,000$).
- There is a simultaneous influence of motivation, work discipline, reward, punishment, organizational culture and leadership on employee job satisfaction at the Tolikara District Health Office and has contributed to employee job satisfaction of 89.5% and punishment is the dominant factor of 64 work satisfaction. , 6%.

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